

EGU22-3821, updated on 13 Jun 2022

<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-3821>

EGU General Assembly 2022

© Author(s) 2022. This work is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

Establishing a zero-pollution circular economy: an overview of the Horizon2020-Green Deal project PROMISCES

Julie Lions¹, Ulf Miehe², Veronika Zhiteneva², Anne Togola¹, Hans Groot³, Martine Bakker⁴, Eric D. van Hullebusch⁵, Valeria Dulio⁶, Michiel Zjip⁴, Nicole Heine⁷, Thomas Track⁷, Alexander Sperlich⁸, Matthias Zessner⁹, Carme Bosch¹⁰, Francesco Fatone¹¹, Stefan Colombano¹, Lidia Fernandez-Rojo¹⁰, and Philippe Negrel¹

¹Brgm, French Geological Survey, Orléans, France (j.lions@brgm.fr)

²Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin gGmbH (KWB), Cicerostrasse 24, 10709 Berlin, Germany

³DELTAES, Boussinesqweg 1, 2629HV Delft, Netherlands

⁴Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM); Antonie van Leeuwenhoeklaan 9, 3721 MA Bilthoven, The Netherlands

⁵Université de Paris, Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris, CNRS, UMR 7154, F-75238, Paris, France

⁶Institut national de l'environnement industriel et des risques (INERIS), France

⁷DECHEMA e.V., Theodor-Heuss-Allee 25, 60486 Frankfurt/Main, Germany

⁸Berliner Wasserbetriebe (BWB), Neue Jüdenstrasse 1, 10179 Berlin, Germany

⁹TU Wien, Institut for Water Quality and Resources Management, Karlsplatz 13, 1040 Vienna, Austria

¹⁰EURECAT, Centre Tecnològic de Catalunya, Plaça de la Ciència, 2, 08242, Manresa, Spain

¹¹Department SIMAU, Università Politecnica delle Marche (UnivPM), Via Brecce Bianche 12, 60121, Ancona, Italy

The PROMISCES project aims to understand the origins, routes and fates of industrial persistent, mobile and potentially toxic pollutants (iPM(T)s), including per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). These substances, also called “forever chemicals”, can be harmful to the environment, human health and circular economy resources.

PROMISCES will develop, test and demonstrate, new technologies and innovations to prevent, monitor and remediate iPM(T)s in the soil-sediment-water system under real-life conditions in the field. In this way, PROMISCES will establish more cost-effective, sustainable and ecological technologies for remediating PFAS and iPM(T)s.

The project will support the European Green Deal goals and sustainability roadmap of urbanised areas by reducing the environmental impacts on waters (surface and groundwater, urban runoff, drinking waters, wastewater, landfill leachate), soils (contaminated sites, brownfields) and dredged sediments (river, seaports) and of nutrient and material recovery (from sewage sludge to recovered fertilisers, dredged sediments to valorised materials, reclaimed water to crops).

To pursue this objective, PROMISCES is centered around seven representative case studies in different European regions linked with challenging chemical pollution, including locations in Spain, Italy, Bulgaria, France, Germany and the Danube river basin between Vienna and Budapest.

This Horizon2020-Green Deal project will address key technological challenges while also developing recommendations for implementing relevant EU plans - such as the Zero Pollution Action Plan, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the EU chemicals strategy for sustainability - and EU policy directives, such as the Sewage Sludge Directive and the Water Framework Directive.